

THE ROLE OF THE AUDIO-LINGUAL METHOD IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract:

This article describes the methods of effective teaching of English among students using the principles of the audio lingual method. Also it provides information on the characteristics and oral drills of the audio lingual method.

Key words: method, teaching, students, learn, teachers, speaking, listening, skills, improve, understand, effective, memorize.

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The audio-lingual method is a method for foreign language teaching which emphasized the teaching of listening and speaking before reading and writing. This method based on Behaviorisms: language learning should become automatic habit formation through drill and pattern practice. I will support this views with argument in the following paragraphs.

This method is combination between behavioral psychology and linguistic. It is also called Army method. The main objective of audio lingual method is to help learners or students acquire accurate pronunciation. Behaviorist lingual method focuses on structure. So audio lingual method helps us to improve our English through listening and speaking skills. Listening activity process include four steps.

They are hearing, understanding, evaluating and responding.

1. Hearing-it deals with a series of sounds that involves with the words and sentences

2. Understanding it means that the meaning of those words and sentences are understood

3. Evaluating-it means that the meaning gained is evaluated the total communication is accepted or rejected

4. Responding-a response is made to what is heard by further through bodily movement facial expression or audible reaction.

Applied to language instruction, and often within the context of the language lab, it means that the instructor would present the correct model of a sentence and the students would have to repeat it. The teacher would then continue by presenting new words for the students to sample in the same structure. In audio-lingualism, there is no explicit grammar instruction: everything is simply memorized in form. The idea is for the students to practice the particular construct until they can use it spontaneously. The lessons are built on static drills in which the students have little or no control on their own output; the teacher is expecting a particular response and not providing the desired response will result in a student receiving negative feedback. This type of activity, for the foundation of language learning, is in direct opposition with communicative language teaching. Charles Carpenter Fries, the director of the

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English Language Institute at the University of Michigan, the first of its kind in the United States, believed that learning structure or grammar was the starting point for the student. In other words, it was the students' job to recite the basic sentence patterns and grammatical structures. The students were given only "enough vocabulary to make such drills possible." [3]. Fries later included principles of behavioral psychology, as developed by B.F. Skinner, into this method. Inflection: Teacher: I ate the sandwich. Student: I ate the sandwiches. Replacement: Teacher: He bought the car for half-price. Student: He bought it for half-price. Restatement: Teacher: Tell me not to smoke so often. Student: Don't smoke so often! The following example illustrates how more than one sort of drill can be incorporated into one practice session: "Teacher: There's a cup on the table ... repeat Students: There's a cup on the table Teacher: Spoon Students: There's a spoon on the table Teacher: Book Students: There's a book on the table Teacher: On the chair Students: There's a book on the chair etc." In the next paragraph, I will write about the characteristic of the audio lingual method:

- Language learning is habit information
- Mistakes are bad and should be avoided as they are considered bad habits.
- Language skills are learned more effectively if they are presented orally first, then in written form.

- Analogy is a better foundation for language learning than analysis. The meanings of words can be learned only in a linguistic and cultural context.

Next, I will give brief information about oral drills:

- Repetition: the student repeats an utterance as soon as she hears it.
- Inflection: one word in a sentence appears in another form when repeated.
- Replacement: one word is replaced by another.
- Restatement: the student rephrases an utterance.

The audio lingual method focuses on speaking and listening competence stressing repetition and habit formation to learn a second or a foreign language. This method makes the learner understand the second language by memorizing and practicing speaking with drilling from the people communication.

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